

THE ROLE OF NATIONAL EXCELLENCE IN MODERN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

Adhamjon Abdurashidov Abduhamitovich,

Associate Professor, Kokand State Pedagogical Institute, PhD

E-mail: adkhamabdurashidov@gmail.com

Abstract:

The competitiveness of the state is based on the full use of its scientific, educational and scientific-technical potential, the development of all sectors of the country through the widespread introduction of innovations into the economy, comprehensive support for small businesses and folk crafts, the creation of the necessary benefits for young people in this area, with special attention paid to the development of their entrepreneurial skills. In particular, the formation of entrepreneurial skills from the preschool education system is a pressing problem of modern pedagogical science.

Keywords: competitiveness of the state, scientific, educational and scientific-technical potential, innovations, small entrepreneurship, folk craftsmanship, preschool education.

INTRODUCTION

The effectiveness of any reform aimed at the benefit of society and humanity directly depends on the potential of specialists being trained in the education system. Therefore, one of the main tasks has become the creation of a personnel training system built on a national basis and based on the experiences of educational development in advanced countries in the world, capable of training high-quality personnel.

The task of conveying the basics of national crafts to educators working in the preschool education and upbringing system and instilling them in the minds of the younger generation through their practical application is becoming an urgent task of modern preschool education. After all, folk crafts are considered one of the most ancient and important types of our material culture, and are intertwined with many areas of fine and applied art.

Folk crafts are a type of national-traditional small-scale production of goods, an industry based on individual and manual labor using simple tools, and a general name for professions in which such products are made. It was widespread before the emergence of large-scale industrial production, and some areas were preserved later. It still occupies an important place in the national economy of underdeveloped countries. However, the specificity, methods, and characteristics of fine and applied arts, the process of artistic processing of objects, and folk crafts differ from each other.

In recent years, local applied arts and crafts have been gaining popularity both in our country and abroad. The state provides comprehensive support to the industry, creating new opportunities for the revival and wide distribution of traditional production of national products. Thus, on June 12, 2023, the Presidential Decree “On measures to widely involve the population in crafts and create favorable conditions for the development of craft activities” was signed. After all, the government resolutions adopted in our country are aimed at the revival of folk crafts. Work in this area has gained particular momentum in recent years, craftsmen have been exempted from established taxes and customs duties. In addition, the “Khunarmand” association is carrying out its activities in order to unite representatives of this direction, protect their rights and obligations, and objectively evaluate their work. The organization makes a significant contribution to the comprehensive support of artists and the search for talented people. Markets

have been built and put into operation in cities and districts, and appropriate trading outlets have been opened, allowing the sale of products produced by the population. Conditions are being created for artisans to freely use cash registers and trading terminals, in accordance with the rules of trade, and to collect cash receipts in commercial banks.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The theoretical foundations of small business and private entrepreneurship and the problems of its development have been studied by Uzbek scientists B.Yu. Khodiev, I.A. Bakieva, A.Yo. Ostonov, S. Parmonov, Q.H. Muftaydinov, N.S. Kasimova, M.S. Kasimova, etc. The pedagogical features of the formation of economic knowledge and entrepreneurial skills in students and young people are reflected in the studies of N.A. Kamalova, S. Bobokulov, R.R. Khakimov and A.B. Nizamov.

Analyses of national crafts have shown that certain aspects of crafts and entrepreneurship in our country have been studied from a scientific and historic perspective in the studies of H.Z.Ziyoev, G.A.Ahmadjonov, H.N.Bobobekov, Sh.Kh.Vohidov, Q.Rajabov, N.Abdurahimova, Z.E.Azimova, M.B.Artiqova, X.T.Azizov, G.A.Agzamova and others.

Among the psychological scientists, G.I.SHchukina, M.G.Davletshin, E.G'.Goziev, V.M.Karimova, R.I.Sunnatova, Z.T.Nishonova, and others expressed their views on the psychological aspects of the problem, while the issue of pedagogical facilitation was covered in the works of P.Nummi, D.Yoldosheva, and N.M.Egamberdieva.

By the resolution of the Head of our state "On measures to attract the population to handicrafts and create favorable conditions for the development of handicraft activities", for craftsmen included in the "National Catalog of Masters of Folk

Applied Arts" and the "Register of Craftsmen Operating in the Tourism Sector" until January 1, 2025, the tax rates on the sale of handicraft products until January 1, 2025: for amounts exceeding 100 million soums (but not exceeding one billion) will be reduced by 50 percent;

State registration of trademarks is free of charge.

The implementation of programs for the development of each area of craft activity in the regions, the preservation of disappearing types of crafts have been identified as the priority tasks of the "Hunarmand" association. In this regard, it is especially worth noting that the organization serves to ensure the continuity of noble professions passed down from generation to generation. Thus, more than 30 percent of the association's members are young men and women, children of independent Uzbekistan. They work in about a dozen areas and together produce more than a thousand different products.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

It is worth noting that, as a result of the awareness of national identity and increased attention to preserving the heritage of our ancestors, national crafts are developing rapidly. This sector has become more refined, enriched in content, and has become an important sector of our economy. If earlier craftsmen encountered various obstacles in selling and displaying their products, today artisans' guilds operate in every region of our country, and special stalls have been organized in the markets. All this means that Uzbek national crafts, which have been preserved for centuries, are not only a source of investment for enterprises operating in this field, but also mean preserving advanced processes in the field in the future. After all, in many corners of our beloved land, which have been centers of national crafts for centuries, traditional types of applied art, which were the cradle of the development of folk crafts, have been preserved today. Looking at the original works that are considered the property of the Republic, it is hard to believe that everything was

different just a few decades ago.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

High intellectual and physical maturity requires the upbringing of young people who are aware of the scientific, technical and economic foundations of production processes and have a conscious and creative attitude to labor, and from a pedagogical point of view, research into the development of entrepreneurial skills through national crafts creates the need to conduct research starting from the preschool education and upbringing system.

In implementing these tasks, we rely on our national traditions formed over the centuries, the rich heritage of our ancestors, and the achievements of the current period of development.

Solving the problems of developing small businesses and entrepreneurship, creating the necessary conditions for the broad involvement of young people, graduates of vocational colleges and universities in this area, also occupies a special place in the continuing education system today. It is precisely in the development of entrepreneurship that it is necessary to study the specific aspects of the continuing education system, in addition to the information related to it.

The organization of small business and entrepreneurship in our country, including the development of national crafts, as an important factor of economic growth and the prospective development of the middle class, not only contributes to increasing the national and spiritual potential of society, but also ensures the increase of national wealth, the integration of the economy into the world system and socio-economic stability. Thus, great attention is paid to the development of pottery, forging, goldsmithing, artistic embroidery, woodcarving, jewelry, and national fabric crafts. It is no less important that, thanks to the efforts of our country's masters, events in this area have become prestigious, have reached an international level, have attracted the attention of the general public, and have attracted thousands of foreign

tourists. All these achievements are the result of the attention and care shown to craftsmen. Thus, several hundred members of the association have state awards. As industry representatives note, such attention encourages them to achieve even greater heights in their creative activities.

Home-based crafts are becoming widespread in neighborhoods and settlements, becoming a stable source of income for representatives of socially vulnerable segments of the population. It is also pleasing to see how much interest young people show in folk crafts, in learning the methods of creating real examples of applied art. Products created by young craftsmen have been repeatedly exhibited at city, regional, republican and international exhibitions in the past year. Indeed, the masters are putting all their efforts into preserving and expanding the rich heritage. Such activities can be called fully active entrepreneurship, because craftsmen create jobs, fill the market with popular goods that are in high demand both in the republic and abroad.

Today, it is easy for creative people to implement business initiatives. A number of new tax incentives have been granted in our country, urgent issues related to the organization of the activities of craftsmen have been resolved, and assistance is being provided for the wide popularization of their products, including in foreign markets. Special attention is being paid to simplifying the use of credit resources for the development of entrepreneurship in the field of applied arts.

Craftsmen will be able to use bank loans on preferential terms. Thus, in 2023, at least 70% of the funds allocated to home-based businesses within the framework of family entrepreneurship development programs will be directed to financing handicraft projects. The Home-Based Business Support Fund has been renamed the Handicraft and Home-Based Business Support Fund. Since June 15, 2023, financial support for the direction has been provided by the fund. At the same time, the document also approved the list of directions of handicraft activities, subsidies,

exhibitions, festivals and international conferences to be held in 2023-2024.

After all, the types of applied arts and crafts that have been preserved among the people and continued by masters are of great importance for understanding our national identity and continuing our national way of life.

RECOMMENDATIONS

National crafts are a direct expression of the life of the people, reflecting the understanding of our people about social life, their high taste, aesthetic views, and at the same time important aspects of folk pedagogy related to moral education. They also reveal the long history, traditions, broad worldview, and hopes of our people in all their grandeur and depth, providing broad and deep knowledge about them and are an important source of interest in spiritual and moral values.

Today, applied art, which was formed on our land many centuries ago, is an integral part of the world's intangible cultural heritage. Its unique examples and the exchange of experience in this field serve to further strengthen friendship and cooperation between peoples, cultural and humanitarian ties, and to restore and preserve the traditions of craftsmen and craft schools.

It is evident that the opportunities provided serve not only to expand or develop their businesses, but also to teach the younger generation how to continue the unique traditions of our ancestors.

The development of entrepreneurial skills through national crafts is to form a conscious attitude towards work. To achieve this goal, it is advisable to positively solve the following tasks:

- instilling the desire to work from preschool education and upbringing and systematically preparing them for years to conduct entrepreneurial activities in various areas of modern production;
- Developing the intellectual abilities of preschool education and upbringing students through the development of entrepreneurial skills through national crafts.

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